

BELL'S PALSY AND AYURVEDA: A CASE STUDY ON THE EFFICACY OF AYURVEDIC TREATMENT FOR ARDITA (BELL'S PALSY)

Dr. Nandlal Saste^{1*}, Dr. S. B. Jamdhade², Dr. Pradnya Jamdhade³

*¹P.G. Scholar, Kayachikitsa Department, ²Professor and H.O.D, Kayachikitsa Department

³Assistant Professor, Department of Dravyaguna,

DMM Ayurved Mahavidhyalaya, Yavatmal, Maharashtra, India.

Article Received on 05 Jan. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Jan. 2026,
Article Published on 01 Feb. 2026,

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18480432>

*Corresponding Author

Dr. Nandlal Saste

P.G. Scholar, Kayachikitsa
Department, DMM Ayurved
Mahavidhyalaya, Yavatmal,
Maharashtra, India.

How to cite this Article: Dr. Nandlal Saste^{1*}, Dr. S. B. Jamdhade², Dr. Pradnya Jamdhade³ (2026). Bell's Palsy And Ayurveda: A Case Study On The Efficacy Of Ayurvedic Treatment For Ardita (Bell's Palsy) "World Journal of Pharmaceutical Research, 15(3), 1596–1604.

This work is licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license.

ABSTRACT

Background: Bell's palsy is a sudden weakness or paralysis of the facial muscles on one side, caused by a problem with the facial nerve. This leads to drooping of the mouth, difficulty closing the eye, and facial asymmetry. In Ayurveda, a similar condition is called Ardita, which happens due to an imbalance of Vata dosha. **Objective:** To see how well Ayurvedic treatment works in managing Ardita (Bell's palsy). **Methods:** This study reports the case of a 70-year-old man with right-side facial weakness, incomplete eye closure, puffiness, drooling, and disturbed sleep for 5 days. He was treated for 15 days with Panchakarma therapies—Shirodhara with Brahmi taila, Mukhabhyanga with Mahanarayan taila, and Nasya with Panchendriya vardhan taila, Netratarpan with Triphala Ghritam—along with internal Ayurvedic medicines such as Yograj guggulu, Aarogyavardhini vati, Sutshekhar rasa, and herbal powders (churna). **Results:** After treatment, there was clear improvement in facial movement, eye closure, and mouth position. The deviation of the mouth and incomplete eye

closure reduced from severe (grade 4) to mild (grade 1), and drooling stopped completely.

Conclusion: This case shows that a combined Ayurvedic approach can help improve symptoms of Ardita quickly and may be a useful option for managing Bell's palsy.

KEYWORDS: Ayurveda, Ardita, Bell's palsy.

INTRODUCTION

Bell's palsy is an acute, idiopathic, unilateral lower motor neuron type of facial nerve paralysis, characterized by sudden onset of facial muscle weakness on one side, often accompanied by inability to close the eye, drooping of the mouth corner, and loss of nasolabial fold. The global annual incidence is approximately 15–30 cases per 100,000 population, with no significant gender predilection.^[1] The exact cause remains uncertain, but viral infections (e.g., herpes simplex virus) and inflammation of the facial nerve within the fallopian canal are implicated.^[2] There is facial asymmetry, deviation of the mouth, drooping of eyelids, improper eye closure of the affected side (on attempting closure, eyeball rolls upward - Bell's phenomenon), difficulty in chewing, drooling of saliva. Taste sensation may be affected unilaterally on the same side.^[3]

In Ayurveda, a similar condition is described as Ardita, a disease affecting half of the face, leading to distortion and impairment of normal movement due to Vata dosha aggravation.^[4]

‘अर्दयत्यनिलो वक्त्रं अर्दितं जनयत्यतः ।’- मा.नि./वातव्याधि/45.^[5]

Ardita is described as one of 80 Nanatmaja Vyadhis^[6] of Vata. According to Charaka Samhita, in Ardita (facial paralysis), symptoms appear on one side of the face and may sometimes involve the body^[7] Sushruta Samhita states that only the face is affected.^[8] Ayurvedic management focuses on calming aggravated Vata through Snehana (oleation), Swedana (sudation), Nasya, Panchakarma, and suitable internal medicines.

‘अर्दिते नावनं मूर्ध्नि तैलं तर्पणमेव च।

नाडीस्वेदोपनाहाश्चाप्यानूपपिशितैर्हिताः ॥ - च.चि. 28/96.^[9]

Integrating Ayurvedic approaches with early diagnosis and appropriate supportive care may help in reducing morbidity and improving functional recovery in Bell's palsy/Ardita patients. This article presents an overview and case-based discussion on Ayurvedic management of Ardita.

AIMS AND OBJECTIVES

To evaluate efficacy of ayurvedic management of Ardita (Bell's Palsy).

MATERIAL AND METHOD

Present work is based on a review of Classical information, relevant Published research work and modern literature.

Method: single case study.

Place: PG department of kayachikitsa laxmanrao kalasapurkar Ayurvedic college Yavatmal, Affiliated with D. M.M Ayurved college yavatmal.

Case Report – A 70 years male patient came to OPD of kayachikitsa department With chief complaints of

1. Mukhshotha (puffiness of face)
2. Dakshin Akshi srav (watering from right eye)
3. Unable to close right eye completely
4. Anidra (disturbed sleep)
5. Angamarda

All complaints are developed since 5 days

History of Present Illness

Patient was said to be healthy before 5days Then he suffered from Mukhshotha (puffiness of face), Dakshin Akshi srav (watering from right eye) Unable to close right eye completely, Anidra (disturbed sleep), Angamarda. He consulted with a local hospital in his area but did not find any relief. So he Approached our L. K. Ayurveda Hospital and was admitted on 04/01/2025 for further management.

PAST HISTORY OF ILLNESS

Patient is known case of Hypertension and taking Tablet CTD-T 12.5/40 mg OD

No history of – DM, Asthma, Thyroid disorder.

Surgical History- Right eye Cataract 4 months ago.

Family History: Not specific.

General Examination

Pulse – 102/min

BP – 140/90mm of Hg

R.R. – 18/min

Wt. – 51.9kg

S/E

RS – B/L Clear

CVS – S1 S2 Normal

CNS – Conscious Oriented

P/A – Soft N/T

Ashtavidha Pariksha

Nadi- 102/min

Mala – Samyak

Mutra-Samyak,

Jivha – Niram

Shabda – Spashta

Sparsha – Samshitoshna

Druka – Prakrut

Akruti – Madhyam

INVESTIGATION

Hb - 12.9gm %, **TLC** - 9960/mm³, **PLATELET**- 1.99 lack /mm³, **RBS** - 95 mg/dl., **Sr. CREATININE** -2mg/dl, **TOTAL CHOLESTEROL** - 173mg/dl, **TRIGLYCERIDE** - 138 mg/dl, **LDL**-101Mg/dl.

SAMPRAPTI GHATAKA^[10]

Dosha -Vata predominant Tridosha

Dushya - Rasa, Rakta, Mamsa, Sira.

Srotas -Rasavaha, Raktavaha

Srotodushti- Sanga, Vimarggaman

Adhistan -Mukhardha

Agni -Vishamagni

DIAGNOSIS- With the above clinical presentation patient is diagnosed as **Dakshin Ardita**.

TREATMENT

Panchakarma Treatment

- Shirodhara with Bramhi Tailam
- Mukh abhyanga with Mahanarayan Tailam
- Nasya with panchendriya vardhan Taila
- Netratarpan with triphala Ghritam

Shaman Chikitsa Table

Dravya	Matra (Dose)	Sevankala	Anupana
Yograj Guggulu	500 mg	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Aarohyavardhini	250 mg	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Sutshekhar rasa	250 mg	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Vatvidhwansa Rasa	250 mg	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Ekangveera rasa	250 mg	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Dashmool churna	1 gm	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Rasana churns	1 gm	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Bramhi churna	1 gm	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Vacha churna	1 gm	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Ashwagandha churna	1 gm	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala
Panchasakar churna	3 gm	Nishakale	Koshnajala
Dashmool bharad kwath	30 ml	Vyanodane (BD)	Koshnajala

RESULTS

The patient showed marked improvement after 15 days of Ayurvedic treatment. Facial symmetry improved significantly.

Assessment criteria^[11]

House–Brackmann Facial Nerve Grading System

I - Normal - Normal facial function in all areas

II - Mild dysfunction - Slight weakness noticeable only on close inspection; complete eye closure with minimal effort; slight asymmetry of smile

III - Moderate dysfunction - Obvious weakness, but not disfiguring; noticeable but not severe asymmetry; complete eye closure with effort; slight mouth movement

IV - Moderately severe dysfunction - Obvious disfiguring asymmetry; incomplete eye closure; asymmetry of mouth with maximum effort

V - Severe dysfunction- Barely perceptible motion; incomplete eye closure; slight mouth movement

VI- Total paralysis - No movement at all

Parameter	Before treatment	After treatment
Deviation of mouth towards right side	Grade 4	Grade 1
Incomplete closure of right eye	Grade 4	Grade 1
Raising of eyebrows	Grade 4	Grade 1
Dribbling of water while drinking	Present	Absent

Overall, the patient experienced improvement in facial muscle control, eye closure, speech clarity, and chewing ability. No adverse effects were noted during the treatment period.

DISCUSSION

Bell's palsy often gets better on its own, but quick treatment can help speed up recovery and prevent long-term problems. Modern treatment usually involves steroids, antiviral medicines,

and physiotherapy. Ayurveda approaches it differently—by balancing Vata dosha, improving nerve function, and restoring muscle strength.

In this case, treatment included Shirodhara, Mukhabhyanga, Nasya and Netratarpana.

1. Shirodhara with Brahmi Taila

Shirodhara is considered a Murdhni Taila therapy that pacifies Vata and Pitta in the head region, nourishes the sense organs (indriya), and promotes mental calmness. Brahmi (*Bacopa monnieri*) has medhya (neurotonic) and rasayana (rejuvenating) properties, improving nerve conduction and brain function.

2. Mukhabhyanga with Mahanarayan Taila

Facial massage with Mahanarayan Taila improves srotoshodhana (channel cleansing) and mamsa dhatu nourishment. It relieves stambha (stiffness) and improves gati (movement) of muscles. Mahanarayan Taila contains ingredients like Ashwagandha, Dashmool, and Bala, known for vatashamaka (Vata-pacifying) and balya (strength-promoting) effects.

3. Nasya with Panchendriya Vardhan Taila

Nasya is one of the panchakarma therapies specifically indicated for Urdhva Jatrugata Vikaras (diseases of the head and neck). Administering Panchendriya Vardhan Taila through the nasal route nourishes cranial nerves, improves sensory perception, and strengthens motor function of facial muscles.

4. Netratarpan

Netratarpan is a treatment where medicated ghee is gently applied to the eyes for some time. In Ardita (facial paralysis), this helps by calming and nourishing the nerves and muscles around the face. It reduces inflammation and swelling, improves blood flow, and helps the muscles work better. The treatment also balances the aggravated Vata dosha, which is often the main reason for the weakness and stiffness seen in facial paralysis. Overall, Netratarpan supports healing, relieves symptoms, and helps the face regain strength and normal movement.

- **Yograj Guggulu** – Pacifies Vata, reduces stiffness and pain, improves joint and muscle mobility.
- **Aarogyavardhini Vati** – Improves digestion and metabolism, detoxifies, supports tissue nourishment.
- **Sutshekhar Rasa** – Calms Pitta, reduces stress on nerves, improves digestion.

- **Vatvidhwansa Rasa** – Strong Vata-pacifier, relieves nerve pain and stiffness.
- **Ekangveera Rasa** – Strengthens nerves, improves motor function in paralysis.
- **Dashmool Churna** – Anti-inflammatory, reduces swelling and Vata-related pain.
- **Rasna Churna** – Relieves stiffness and muscle pain, improves mobility.
- **Brahmi Churna** – Enhances nerve function, memory, and brain activity.
- **Vacha Churna** – Stimulates nerves, clears channels, improves speech.
- **Ashwagandha Churna** – Strengthens muscles and nerves, reduces stress.
- **Panchasakar Churna** – Mild laxative, removes Ama (toxins), supports Vata balance.
- **Dashmool Bharad Kwath** – Reduces inflammation, strengthens the nervous system

The internal medicines worked together to reduce Vata aggravation and support nerve healing. Yograj guggulu and Vatvidhwansa rasa are known for their nerve-strengthening and pain-reducing effects, while Dashmool and Ashwagandha help in overall recovery.

Within 15 days, the patient showed major improvement in eye closure, eyebrow movement, and mouth symmetry. This shows that early, multi-step Ayurvedic treatment can be effective in Bell's palsy, especially when started soon after symptoms appear.

CONCLUSION

This case shows that Ayurvedic treatment using Panchakarma therapies and herbal medicines can help restore facial nerve function and improve symptoms of Ardita (Bell's palsy) in a short time. The patient experienced significant recovery within two weeks. More studies with larger numbers of patients are needed to confirm these results and create standard Ayurvedic treatment plans for Bell's palsy.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

“Informed consent was obtained from the patient for publication of clinical details and images.”

REFERENCES

1. Peitersen E. Bell's palsy: the spontaneous course of 2,500 peripheral facial nerve palsies of different etiologies. *Acta Otolaryngol Suppl.*, 2002; (549): 4-30. PMID: 12482166. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/12482166/>

2. Holland NJ, Weiner GM. Recent developments in Bell's palsy. *BMJ.*, 2004 Sep 4; 329(7465): 553-7. doi: 10.1136/bmj.329.7465.553. PMID: 15345630; PMCID: PMC516110. <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/15345630/>
3. Exam preparatory manual for undergraduates 3rd edition, Archith Bolor, Ramdas Nayak, chapter-15, p-1063-1064.
4. Acharya YT, editor. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha, Chikitsa Sthana, 28/33-34. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Sansthan, 2017; 619.
5. Bhishagratna KL, editor. Madhava Nidana of Madhavakara, Vata Vyadhi Nidana, verse 45. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Sanskrit Series Office, 2020; 471.
6. Agnivesh's Charaka Samhita with elaborated Vidyotini Commentary by Kasinatha Sastri and Dr.Gorakha NathChaturvedi, Varanasi, Chaukambha Bharati Academy, reprint edition, Part 1, Suta Sthana, 2013; 20/11.
7. Agnivesh's Charaka Samhita with elaborated Vidyotini Commentary by Kasinatha Sastri and Dr.Gorakha NathChaturvedi, Varanasi, Chaukambha Bharati Academy, reprint edition, Part 2, Chikitsa Sthana, 2013; 28/42.
8. Murthy KRS, editor. Sushruta Samhita of Sushruta, Nidana Sthana, 1/68-70. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia, 2014; 351.
9. Sharma PV, editor. Charaka Samhita of Agnivesha, Chikitsa Sthana, 28/96. Varanasi: Chaukhambha Orientalia, 2017; 623.
10. Shyam B, Kulkarni V, Hugar VM. Management of Ardita through Panchakarma: A Case Study. *Journal of Emerging Technologies and Innovative Research.* 2022; 7. Available from: <https://jetir.org/papers/JETIR2207091.pdf>
11. Sindhu H.V, Abdul Khader. Ardita and its Ayurvedic Management - A True Story. *JAyurveda Integr Med Sci.*, 2024; 3: 260-266. <https://dx.doi.org/10.21760/jaims.9.3.42>.